

Vector backbone: pBluescript KS
PmH4p, *P. multistriata* H4 gene promoter; GFP, green fluorescent protein; MRM1, Mating-type Related Minus 1 gene coding sequence; Gene ID: 0085380/0041130 (Russo et al., 2018); PtLhcf1t, *P. tricornutum* Lhcf1 gene terminator.
This plasmid is suitable for *P. multistriata* biolistic transformation and is used to overexpress and tag the MRM1 gene.